

**“...WISH WE HAD TRIED HARDER”: POST PANDEMIC
NIGERIA, ADMINISTRATIVE AND COMMUNICATION
FRUGALITY ON COVID-19**

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Abstract

The postmodern society is synonymous with a globalized world connected by technology. Thus concerns about the Covid 19 pandemic proliferated worldwide upon its discovery in 2019. It is not possible to claim that there are countries that did not understand the characteristics and increasing difficulties the index countries faced. Therefore, preparedness was imminent. In administration we talk about the place of effective and quality personnel, relevant equipment, infrastructure, proper information management and availability of finance. Whilst these are being put in place, the next focus is the communication of pertinent preventive measures among the populace, mostly those in remote areas of the country towards forestalling the pandemic. This article reveals a wide range of issues the country is struggling now with which brings out the questions: What is the country's responsiveness of public services? How did the country design the management of social order in the hit of the pandemic which is necessary for a healthier society? How did it prepare skills and capacity needed in every angle- medical infrastructure, mobility, and social welfare of the citizens, preventive measures like mask, hand sanitizers and soap among other things? How did the interior ministry prepare for border closures and all within its precinct? What was the set up for markets, health responses of others citizens whether on covid-19 or not. How knowledgeable will the country boast of its citizens on the important issues on Covid-19, which is now scaling up in the once spectating

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country? With the way the pandemic issue is enforcing in Nigeria. What are the strategies of communication for the unprepared populace? Our concern is on the foray into what the country will be post-pandemic. Will our aftermath have the semantic expression of we "wish we had tried harder" in forestalling the covid-19 before it onset in Nigeria. Non-systematic participant observation and review of publish comments on select social media will be applied to this study while Derrida's deconstruction as applied to the issues on ground will help in examining some contexts.

Keywords: Administration, Communication, Covid-19 Pandemic, Deconstruction Management, Post pandemic Nigeria.

Résumé

La société postmoderne est synonyme d'un monde globalisé et connecté par la technologie. C'est pourquoi on s'inquiétait quand la pandémie du Covid 19 a pris le monde entier par surprise dès sa découverte en 2019. On ne prétend pas qu'il existe des pays qui n'ont pas compris les caractéristiques et les difficultés croissantes auxquelles les pays les plus touchés ont vécus. Par conséquent, le préparatif était imminent. En matière d'administration, on parle de la place d'un personnel efficace et de qualité, d'équipements pertinents, d'infrastructures, d'une bonne gestion d'information et de la disponibilité du financement. Pendant qu'on fasse tout pour que ces derniers soient disponibles, l'objectif est d'assurer la mise en place des mesures préventives pertinentes parmi la population, principalement dans les zones éloignées du pays, afin de prévenir la pandémie. Cet article traite des nombreuses questions auxquels le pays est actuellement confronté, ce qui soulève les interrogations suivantes: quelle est la réponse des services publics du pays ? Comment le pays a-t-il conçu la gestion de l'ordre social sous l'impulsion de la pandémie, ce qui est nécessaire pour une société saine? Comment a-t-il préparé les compétences et capacités nécessaires dans tous les domaines - infrastructure médicale, mobilité et bien-être social des citoyens, y compris les mesures préventives comme le masque, les désinfectants pour les mains et le savon, entre autres ? Comment le ministère de l'Intérieur s'est-il préparé à la fermeture des frontières et à l'intérieur du pays? Qu'est-ce qu'on a mis en place pour protéger les marchés, les réponses sanitaires des citoyens que ce soit ceux qui ont le Covid-19 ou non? Dans quelle mesure le pays se vantera-t-il de ses citoyens sur les problèmes liés au Covid-19, les problèmes qui ont pris maintenant de l'ampleur dans ce pays autrefois moins touché? De la manière dont le problème de la pandémie s'applique au Nigeria, quelles sont les stratégies de communication envers la population non préparée? Notre préoccupation est de savoir ce que deviendra le pays après la pandémie. Est-ce que les conséquences auront-elles l'expression sémantique de «nous souhaiterons avoir mis plus

d'efforts» pour prévenir le Covid-19 avant son arrivée au Nigeria. L'observation participante non systématique et l'évaluation des commentaires publiés sur certains médias sociaux seront appliqués à cette étude, tandis que la déconstruction appliquée aux problèmes sur le terrain selon Derrida, aidera à examiner certains contextes.

Mots clés: Administration, communication, pandémie du Covid-19, Gestion de la déconstruction, Nigeria après la pandémie.

Introduction

The idea of making the world more inclusive has been at the fore of the postmodern ideology.

The postmodern ideology can be said to have emanated from French intellectuals like Michel Foucault (1980), Jean Francois Lyotard (1984), Jean Baudrillard (1988) to mention a few. These scholars critique the modern scientific research which is encapsulated in positivism. Coming from a post-positivist angle, they present ideas of which this study finds relevant to appropriate. One of these is Postmodernism. Postmodernism simply stands as a critique of the modern construct and tends to question the structures of the ruling class and the dichotomies modernity created by conventional thought. These scholars concern themselves with the emancipation of and from the ruling discourses and their empirical understanding of truth. Rejecting the grand narrations of the dominant discourses and ideologies of Materialism and Capitalism, they try to create a 'no boundaries' perspectives and ideology that enable people to define their own reality. For them, there is no absolute knowledge 'because what we call knowledge has to be made and other meaning-making resources of a particular culture and different cultures can see the world in very different ways; all of which 'work' in their own terms' (Lemke, 1994, Okam, 2014). This means that truth is relative and truth is up to the individual to determine himself. Therefore, the people should be active in the processes that address their lives.

The idea of making the world more inclusive has been on the fore of postmodern ideology. Where the paradox emerges is that while the inclusiveness depends on technological inventions for such decentralisation. It becomes increasingly supportive of opening more uncontrolled spaces virtually. Therefor all spaces begin to develop versatility in an attempt to interpret or express their innovative possibilities. Clive Beck's idea of Postmodernism as a "general cultural phenomenon" with "such features as challenging of conventions, the mixing of styles, tolerance of ambiguity, and emphasis on diversity of acceptance of innovation and change and stress on the contractedness of reality" (Nwosu, 2014:14) underscores the petrifying fragmentation of an ideology that tends to

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promote inclusion of all sectors of the society. The strangeness of this concept that dismantles convention lies in its power over areas that one could take as an exception, yet it does not permit such exemption.

Taking cue from Frank Diana's statement, in health, "the Spanish flu or 1918 flu pandemic...SARS...Zika virus..." is a figural example of the present coronavirus pandemic Covid-19. While Diana stated that technological inventions and innovations have altered the society, for example the internet, smart phones and increased automation (2020). To this extent, one would not be wrong to say that the unsystematic or rather unconventional characteristics of postmodernism aligns with Jacques Derrida's ideological stance and his appropriation of the literary field through the concept of Deconstruction. To communicate its appropriateness with postmodern ideology is best when one looks at the dashboard of Derrida's Deconstruction.

Ibrahim Alqudah citing Jonathan Culler states that "Deconstruction looks for anything in the text that counters an authoritative interpretation, including interpretations that the word itself appears to encourage" (2019:500). Alqudah believes that for Derrida, "a system of difference precedes any location of meaning in the text" depicting the fact that what is meant is not the real essence but is different from what appears to be meant". In this way, the reading of literary texts in a deconstructive mode is not a matter of decoding the meaning, it is a matter of entering into the constant play of contradiction" (2019:501).

It is in the foregoing pluralist context that frames our idea that Derrida's deconstruction which underscores the paradigmatic construct of postmodernism can help us project argument into the post pandemic situation in Nigeria will look like. However we have to explain what post pandemic means to us.

Research questions

In this connection, this study will attempt to provide answers to the following questions:

- i What are the administrative strengths showcased by the government pre-covid-19 in Nigeria.
- ii What are the responses of the National Orientation Agency to curb the pandemic onset in the country?
- iii. What are the strategies set to communicate to the diverse population in the country plan.
- iv What is the country doing presently and how?
- v. What will be the aftermath of the preparation and execution of activity in the pandemic after the pandemic?
- vi. What are the implications of the country's unpreparedness on the future of the country economically, socially, environmentally etc?

Covid –19 Pandemic Signal, Onset and Post Pandemic Nigeria

Our common experience so far is that in 2019, the world was caught unawares by the coronavirus Covid-19 Pandemic. “Researchers studying the spread of the virus pinpoints COVID-19’s likely origin to a ‘wet market’, or live animal market, in Wuhan, China.”. (Brown, 2020:1). It then spreads to many European countries killing vast majority of people and devastating economies as well as creating global panic. China has been able to put a stop to its prevalence due to the rapid response of the Chinese government Covid-19 “which was confirmed on the 27th of February 2020, is the first case to be reported in Nigeria since the beginning of the outbreak in China in January 2020” (NCDC. 2020:1). Sophe Tanno and Ryan Fahey (2020, 1) quoted Nicholas A.Christakis as saying: that China's unique collectivist culture, and authoritarian government, have allowed it to combat the disease quickly and efficiently” They reported him of stating that “China’s 'deeply impressive' ability to impose movement restrictions on provinces of over 930 million people to prevent the spread of the virus, an astonishing measure which he argued would 'not be easy to reproduce' in the US and elsewhere.” From the above, it becomes clear that the Chinese government has robust communication system, medical system and a responsive governmental will to avert a catastrophe of the covid-19 magnitude.

Our concern, in this study is not to tell already known stories or to compare style of governance but to express the timeliness of measures I to curb a disease that was not envisaged and the effect it will have on the populace. After the Nigerian government had in time past used military force on the Biafra group with recuse. An action which was condemned by many and applauded by those whose intensions it fulfilled. However, whereas the government has not done anything significant to protect the threatening spaces where knowledge-where knowledge about the pandemic is less. While in many countries of the world consultative exercises were carried out by the government on how to tackle the epidemic which was sure to be a pandemic.

The range of Nigeria’s consultation and preparedness could be argued to be austere. Administratively, the Interior ministry did not close the county’s borders both land and air on time, whereas air borders were closed, land borders were left open. It did not commission experts in communication, health (on broad terms) advocacy groups to engage in sensitization and in dialogue with the people through representatives and senators, no national dialogue on the way out to get the little feeling of the lay man who forms a great part of the population.

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We make attempt to present our interest in involving people from Bettina von Lieres and David Kahane's (2007) strategies on "inclusion and representation in democratic deliberations..."

1. The extent to which the administrative process is reflexive, in the sense of giving the common man a deliberative say in defining the terms of their participation the issues of covid-19 which will inadvertently affect them.
2. The extent to which the public involvement is recursive, so that citizen involvement takes place from the beginning, thus enabling the application to the range of decisions made.
3. The existence of spaces in which individuals and groups can reflect on dynamics of arising issues and exclusion, and negotiate questions of common agendas, strategies and eventualities among other issues.

From Deconstructing Realities to Reconstructing a Post Pandemic Future

In constructing the fate of Nigeria post pandemic, we had to look at the very many narratives that have gone with the pandemic period. This is the sense in which one encounters Jacques Derrida's philosophical stance of Deconstruction. Derrida suggested that there is nothing outside context, "Context here can be speech, life, the world, the real, history and what not" In which case according to Nicholas Royle Derrida's "deconstruction would be the effort to take this limitless context into account, and thus to incessant movement of recontextualization"(2003:65). As the title of the article reads "...Wish we had tried harder", this statement made by an American Journalist with CNN, Fareed Zakaria came from his foray into what the post pandemic world would turn out to be if the rest of the world does not come together to help Africa. Melinda Gates in affirmation to Zakaria states:"Its going to be horrible in the developing world. Part of the reasons you are seeing the case numbers still do not look very bad is because they don't have access to many tests. There will be dead bodies all over the streets of Africa... My first thought was Africa. How in the world are they going to deal with this? I have been in townships all over Africa and slums. When we talk in country physical distancing and hand-washing, if you live in slums who can't physical distance, you have to go out and get your meals. You don't have clean water to wash your hands,"(Bolashodun, 2020:1). The statements above are stake reality of the state of Nigeria. But the question is, did Nigeria not find it tasking surviving Ebola and other disease that visited the world. Why do we still lack the sense of organization and proper administration? What is hindering the government from putting up proper communication strategies that will reach both cities and villages?

Suffice it to say that the Health sector was not prepared despite the Minister of Health comment on the preparedness of the country to handle corona virus. According to Kess Ewubare (2020: 1) “the minister of health, assures Nigerians that the health ministry in collaboration with the Lagos state government is well ready to contain the novel coronavirus if eventually the disease eventually breaks out in Nigeria.” His use of “if”, shows the fact that he is putting the possibility of the pandemic getting to Nigeria under probability, and this is the same reason the minister did not ensure doing in other states of the federation and the FCT what the Lagos state government which he is applauding did. To buttress this point, the Secretary to the Government of the Federation has said that “I am not aware that our healthcare system is so bad like this”. Equally disturbing is that the Nigerian President had to be pressurized to address the nation by some section of the mainstream media on the dangers posed by the pandemic.

On the part of information dissemination, Nigeria did not use its information dissemination mechanism to reach a vast number of its population especially those in the rural areas and semi-urban areas. Institutions like the National Orientation Agency (NOA), Federal Radio corporation, agencies known for grassroots mobilization and communication among others across the country where not carried along. Now it is very difficult to achieve this now that the pandemic has set in, unless in areas where the virus has not reached. As Derrida would say” Be alert with these invisible quotations marks, even within a word” (Royle, 2003:2)what then does the actions so far narrated signify? The post pandemic has started glaring its petrifying look into the nation. We look forward to see a nation devastated beyond the relics of the Nigeria civil war of the late 1960s.

Migration, Robbery, banditry, kidnapping and marginalization will be on the high rise as groups will now rise up to see the treatment meted out to them by the ruling class who are predominantly not decentralized. Austerity is a mini word as great depression will loom the country. It will be a case of dystopia. However politicians will use this avenue to change the political voice in the country which may also be a way forward after the suffering. Despite all these, Nigeria will rise as nonpolitical or economic interventions will answer for them. A plus which undermines them will bring out for them. African will not fall.

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COVID 19 Administrative and Communicative imperatives

Administration has to do with coordinating all the process, human, materials, and financial resources for the attainment of set goals. Here you set goals and mobilize the resources available at your disposal to achieve the goals set. Here we find out how the health sector fared. We tried to find out the deficiencies in the administration of the processes involved in health care which include inadequate trained personnel, corruption, and improper coordination from state to state. The nation has suffered Ebola, SARS, Lassa fever so government should prepare for post pandemic measures like catering for the needy, those traumatized psychologically, those who may have lost their jobs or source of livelihood, those who may have lost faith in the nation because of how the pandemic was handled. There may be a significant few who may lose faith with humanity, science and government. How do we manage these myriads of post pandemic issues which are sure to stare us at the face? Will sharing of food continue after the pandemic? Ladipo (2000) says administration should ensure continuity and standardization of policy, continuity comes in the case of post pandemic for government to prepare for the future of any occurrence.

The question must be raised of what should be done in order to promote and enhance the ability of people to cope with the dystopia in a post pandemic Nigeria is expected to face. This is not the responsibility of government alone. Religious organizations, civil society organizations, individual groups who will help to implement and provide community engagement and communication of hope in dystopia should be reached and engaged. The overall aim of this is to ensure that the post pandemic effect will not metamorphose into socio-economic upheaval. The type of education for such times has to be such that government development practitioners and planners have to be involved in tackling, otherwise known as participatory development communication(4) This will also involve community researchers who go into communities with high level of curiosity and analytical capacity and understanding of their own culture, how to research to research among their own people should be conducted; a god traditional education and confidence and respect of the villager. (Von Geusen et al, qtd in Grenier 1998:31) The point of this is to ensure the kind of development that will emanate from the people, sustained by them and make it possible to extend the methods, experiences and gains to others, in what may be called scale-up. Thus, communication approaches like social mobilization, program communication, community theatre, Theatre for Development would be engaged to this effect. For example, Theatre for Development chooses people whose concerns are being studied to do the study themselves, knowing where to resolve controversies and provide an agreeable base of information upon which each party can proceed towards deliberation (Okam, 2015: 57).

Accountability comes in where administrative agents saddled with the responsibility of sharing relieve packages make sure they get to the right persons instead of diverting palliatives for their personal use. In Ihejiamaizu (1996) administration is concerned with how a particular course of action is predetermined by the basic political or policy forming units of the total government, electorate, legislative or executive and how the functions are to be carried out. He holds that it covers activities ranging from determination of what is to be done (policy-making, objective plans) to organization, staffing and financing of government activities as well as final accounting of administrative activity by means of internal and external control. Meaning that administration is a broad based mechanism which draws its strength from the expectations of the government as in provision of basic things needed to fight this virus and being accountable for what is committed into their hands. Like Akpama (2002) puts it, administrative agents are expected to use their administrative discretion in enforcing some of the rules but within the bounds of the law guiding them. For example, in making an arrest of those who violate the lockdown rule the administrative agents are authorized by law to use reasonable force, but where an administrative agent kills a person in the process he or she has exceeded his or her limit of discretion and may face the law. The concept of administrative discretion is related to the due process of the law. Here in Nigeria we have seen cases of administrative agent killing the people they are supposed to protect simply because they violated the lockdown rule. In Delta state the army killed a man because he disobeyed the lockdown rule which made the youth of the area to go on a reprisal attack and killed a soldier. In Abuja a man was killed who went out to look for food for his pregnant wife. When there is abuse of power because you have the opportunity to use the power without discretion it calls for administrative control.

Deconstructive analysis of the aftermath of COVID 19 Pandemic

The extent of damage caused by this pandemic is in magnitude next to none because not even the first and second world wars had far reaching consequences and reverberations through the length and breadth of the five continents Africa, the Americas, Europe, Canada, Asia, the Antarctica Regions of the world. This pandemic is different from other pandemics because:

- i. It came in a subtle and harmless manner but quickly permeated the nations of the world.
- ii. It was an invisible enemy but with potent destructive agenda.
- iii. It took scientists and leaders of nations unawares

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- iv. It struck at the economic base of nations thereby paralyzing economic activities
- v. For the first time in our living memory all nations experienced a lockdown
- vi. This pandemic engendered enormous exasperation, frustration and panic
- vii. It wreaked havoc on developed and advanced nations of the world more than on less developed nations
- viii. It recorded alarming death tolls in different nations that make it the worse world calamity since after the second world war
- ix. Nations have experienced disarticulation in their economies, family structure, individual finances, public and private businesses, life style, social alignments.
- x. Spiritual, Religious and social understandings have been affected positively and negatively- for instance many now have abandoned science to seek help from God while some feel that God has failed to deliver them and need to either remain agnostic, irreligious, secular or indifferent. Science and God appear to have failed.
- xi. But a more positive and realistic outlook is that the plague has visited the world because of what Bishop Berkeley calls the evils of Atheism, irreligion, superstition, Scientism, and Idolatry. It is a call to return to our creator and live our lives according to the rules He has laid for us. That is, to turn away from our sinful ways.

Amidst confusion what mankind needs is a studied and rational contemplation and assessment of what we had been through as we passed through the "valley of the shadow of death" these excruciating five months. The questions are:

- i. Are we going to come away with some lessons from what happened?
- ii. Is the world going to learn some very fundamental lessons as to our humanity and limitations?
- iii. Are we going to see reasons to nurture a world without hate, racism, exploitation and corruption?
- iv. Are we going to see the uselessness of international diplomacy that is adversarial and pugnacious?
- v. Is there still any need for the stock pile of armaments and war heads where a small virus can destroy the world in a matter of months?
- vi. Is there any justification for the bellicosity of superpowers and the subtle engineering of wars in and among nations?

- vii. Is the cost of provoking God not higher than the pecuniary, economic, or political benefits accruing to nations who cause wars, shed innocent blood in order to sale their weapons of mass destruction?
- viii. Is the vanity of earthly pursuit not made obvious by the devastation made by this virus in the world in a matter of months?

The immediate pandemic issues will be how to recover broken economies at the national, corporate and individual levels. How to make the humans of the world to have their wounds healed and their psychological traumas assuaged on account of death of parents, relations, friends and colleagues. How do we contend with the fear and panic this experience has entrenched in the hearts of men? Is there hope that people will repose their hope wholeheartedly on science after now?

On the positive side the concern of nations and humanity should be how to enhance, consolidate and cement the “camaraderic” humanistic spirit of sharing and fellow-feeling engendered by the pandemic. How do we build greater solidarity and friendship? How do we pull down the wall of partition between races, atavistic alignments on old -war- path among nations? How do we destroy the cold war between Russia and United States and their allies? Is it possible to return to God the creator of mankind and live according to His eternal and just rules?

We have seen how fragile national economies are; we have seen the depth of injustice in the distribution of the Commonwealth of Nations. While some had food stockpiled to carry them for months and years, others could not survive the lockdown for a day. This is the degree of inequality, the disparity and the volume of number of the world’s poor that the pandemic has exposed.

It calls for a more humane and realistic administrative structure at all levels of our national life and world structure to redress the obvious imbalance thrown up by this pandemic.

This will require seasoned Administration in our economy, social life (welfare issues) spiritual issues, political intergovernmental affairs, home affairs. Administration entails coordinating, managing and harnessing all resources materials, financial, human to achieve set goals. We have seen how porous, empty and misdirected our administrative goals are. They suffer from misplaced priorities and the wealthy centered approach to administration. The pandemic received quick and comprehensive attention because it targeted mostly the wealthy and the highly placed. For Morris Johnson; the Prime minister of Britain, Angela Merkel of Germany, the President of Monaco and some highly placed in Nigeria including some governors were not so lucky. The lessons we have learnt are that ad hoc administrative arrangement will not suffice in future emergencies

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of breathtaking dimension, a well trained corps of health professionals must always be on hand, there has to be well equipped hospitals, quarantine centers, inter State liaison officers, rehabilitation programmes, proper coordination of palliative distribution, good communication network, enlightenment programmes, inbuilt mechanism to limit corruption and an atmosphere that is conducive for the politicization of matters of grave national importance such as this pandemic.

Communication of health matters becomes of first importance because it is health first. This will mean more sensitization, program communication, town hall meetings, sensitization and advocacy even through social media, harnessing the social, economic, religious and political circles to be interveners in the process of recovery. When the sector relations and power relations within the country are significantly engaged eradication dystopia will be fast..

Conclusion

We have endeavored to carry out both a deconstructive and reconstructive appraisal of covid 19 pandemic in Nigeria. It is a panoramic and systematic account of the unpreparedness, ineptitude and the 'ad-hocism' that characterized the confrontation of the index case that greeted the soil of Nigeria. The concern of this paper is to ascertain whether at the end of this pandemic it will be a tale of woes, of regrets or negative postmortem. Our verdict is that the outcome will be a mixed grill of the good and the bad. So far we can say that there has been some fairly good showing by the government. Real efforts have been made by the government in line with the recommendations and guidelines made by W.H.O. In our deconstructive attempt, it is obvious that there are a lot of loopholes, loose ends, missteps, and stampede without inclusiveness which has hampered and militated against wholesale mobilization of the populace in the fight against the virus. Definitely there will be cases where we would regret some bad consequences resulting from mishandling, misapplication or abuse of certain ground rules in checkmating the pandemic. What is important is that we would have learnt some salient lessons for possible future experience. But going by the Ebola experience we can say that Nigeria hardly benefits from hindsight but enjoys badly managed situations so that some smart guys can have a rip off on the nation through misappropriation of funds. However, we acknowledge sincere efforts by genuine Nigerians in the health sector, government, and private sector, those in Diaspora who through their efforts brought spirited fight against the pandemic. Our recommendation is that our government and the health sector should be more proactive and responsive in future emergencies like the one the world is presently enmeshed in.

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